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Prevalence And Correlate Of Postpartum Depression Among Postnatal Women In Rivers State

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ABSTRACT

This study was on prevalence and correlates of postpartum depression among postnatal women in Rivers state. The study adopted the ex-post facto as well as the correlational research design in the study. The population of the study consisted of 3,241 postnatal mothers in the selected hospitals in Rivers State which includes University of Port Harcourt teaching Hospital (UPTH), Rivers State University Teaching Hospital, Military Hospital and Obio Cottage Hospital. The sample size for the study was 200 postnatal women drawn using non-proportionate and purposive sampling technique. Two instruments were used in the study which are “Prevalence and Correlates of Postpartum Depression Questionnaire” (PCOPDQ) and the “Edinburgh Postnatal Depression Scale” (EPDS). Furthermore, in order to identify mothers with postpartum depression, those who score up to 15 and above were considered as experiencing PPD and vice-versa. Validity of the instruments was determined by giving it to experts in Measurement for vetting. Cronbach Alpha method was used in determining the reliability of the instrument which yielded reliability coefficients of 0.81 and 0.71, respectively for the “PCOPDQ” and “EPDS” respectively. Descriptive statistics involving simple percentage, mean, standard deviation as well as Pearson Product Moment Correlation was used to analyze the data collected in the process. Findings showed that there is a moderate prevalence of postpartum depression among postnatal women in Rivers state, out of 200 respondents, only 76 cases were revealed. Also, it was shown that there is a significant influence of spousal support ($p=0.021<0.05$) on postpartum depression among postnatal women in Rivers State. Based on this, it was recommended among others that government should subsidize the cost of antenatal services to bridge the gap that may arise as a result of inability to afford medical bills.

Keywords: Prevalence, Socio-economic status, Correlate, Postpartum depression, Postnatal women.

INTRODUCTION

The birth of a baby can start a variety of powerful emotions, from excitement and joy to fear and anxiety. It can also result in something one might not expect which is depression. Depression is a common but serious mood disorder. Depression symptoms can interfere with one’s ability to work, sleep, study, eat, and enjoy one’s life. Postpartum depression is an umbrella term, which encompasses several mood disorders that follow childbirth within 6 weeks. Most new mothers experience postpartum “baby blues” after childbirth, which commonly include mood swings, crying spells, anxiety and difficulty in sleeping. Having a baby is a life-changing experience. Being a parent is exciting but can also be tiring and overwhelming. It’s normal to have feelings of worry or doubt, especially if one is a first-time parent. However, if one’s feelings include extreme sadness or loneliness, severe mood swings and frequent crying spells, one may have postpartum depression (Robertson, Grace, Wallington & Stewart 2013).

Postpartum depression (PPD) is a type of depression that happens after someone gives birth. It is characterized by symptoms such as tearfulness, a feeling of hopelessness, emotional liability, feelings of guilt, sleep problems and loss of appetite. Postpartum depression is a non-psychotic depressive episode, beginning within 4 weeks after childbirth (O'Hara & Wisner 2014).

As joyful and as exciting as the birth of a baby can be to a mother, it can be emotionally draining, tiring, and stressful leading to a depressed mood which affects a woman's quality of life, social functioning and economic productivity. Postpartum depression is a very real and serious problem for many mothers. It can happen to a first-time mothers or veteran mother. It can occur a few days or a few months after child birth. Some new mothers experience a more severe, long-lasting form of depression known as postpartum depression. Sometimes it is called peripartum depression because it can start during pregnancy and continue after childbirth. Rarely, an extreme mood disorder called postpartum psychosis also may develop after childbirth. (Adama, Foumane, Olen, Dohbit & Meka 2015).

The American Psychiatric Association (2000), defined postpartum depression as the occurrence of a major depressive episode (MDE) within 4 weeks after delivery and characterized by loss of interest in usual events, sleep challenges, feelings of sadness, fatigability, problems of appetite, and difficulty in coping with daily activities. According to World Health Organization (2018), 10–20% of postnatal mothers suffered from depressive symptoms during their postpartum period. The magnitude of postpartum depression (PPD) raised by 18.4% between 2005 and 2015 years globally (Perfetti, Clark & Fillmore, 2004).

Postpartum depression can affect a mother's capacity to effectively meet her child's basic needs, which can lead to chronic, contrary effects on the child's health and well-being. Mothers who suffer from postpartum depression have changes in their diet, sleep, and activity levels and this can result in the mother being malnourished, exhausted, and overly or less energetic than usual; just as it is with general depression. Postpartum depression is highly prevalent and has a major impact on the health of a mother and child (Cardaillac & Gagnon, 2016). It was reported that depressive disorders in the perinatal period affect women of all cultural and ethnic backgrounds (Klier, Lenz, & Waldhor, 2008).

Furthermore, depression limits the mother's capacity to care for the child, affecting the child's development both physically and mentally ((Klier, Lenz, & Waldhor 2008). The psychological well-being of women during the postnatal period is an important public health concern (Huizink, Robles, Mulder, Visser & Buitelaar 2003).

In Nigeria, the prevalence of postpartum from 2000 to 2019 are as follows: In western Nigeria, a mild and moderate prevalence of postpartum depression reported were 14.6% and 23.0% respectively. Studies were conducted in south-eastern Nigeria and the results were a low prevalence of 10.7% and a moderate prevalence of 30.0%. In Northern Nigeria, a high and moderate prevalence rates of 44.5% and 21.8% respectively were reported (for instance, in kano, the prevalence of depression was found to be 26.6% which was moderate). In Eastern Nigeria, it showed 13.6% mild prevalence of postpartum depression. According to data gathered in maternity centres and clinics in Bayelsa state, the prevalence rate ranged from moderate depression (37.7%), low depression (3.5%) to lower depression (3.2%). According to Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, Rivers State University Teaching Hospital, Port Harcourt, the prevalence rate is 33.3% moderate postpartum depression (Nonye-Enyidah, Jumbo, Enyidah, & Terhemen, (2024). As at April, 2024, the prevalence rate of postpartum depression is 20%. It could also be safe to state that there are a lot of factors which are responsible for post-partum depression among postnatal women. While some may be environmental, some on the other could be hereditary or biological, psychological and even social factors which could contribute to this ugly trend.

Socioeconomic status (SES) refers to an individual's position in a society which is determined by wealth, occupation, and social class and is a measure of an individual's or group's standing in the community. It usually relates to the income, occupation, educational attainment, and wealth of either an individual or a group to the social standing or class of individuals. Socioeconomic status is typically broken into three levels (high, middle, and low) to describe the three places a family or an individual may fall in relation to others (National Institutes of Health 2016). According to Sharan (1986), High economic status indicates a

high-income, high-status occupation and adequate living conditions and may have all it takes to provide for themselves after birth which may take care of any challenges, they would have encountered that may put them into depressive state. On the other hand, mothers from high socio-economic backgrounds are just likely to experience postpartum depression as those from low socioeconomic backgrounds because some studies suggest that women from high socioeconomic backgrounds may be likely to experience postpartum depression due to increased pressure to be a perfect mother, greater emphasis on maintaining a perfect image or body and more intense scrutiny from social media, family and friends etc. Goyal (2002) concluded that mothers who were in a lower socioeconomic status were initially, more likely to develop PPD first. However, at one month postpartum, the mothers in both the low and higher socioeconomic status, were both as likely to develop PPD. They also discovered that mothers with lower socioeconomic status were more likely to not have adequate treatment for this depression, which caused them to have depressive symptoms longer than the mothers that were in a higher socioeconomic status. The risk of developing PPD increased with each additional socioeconomic status factor (Goyal, 2002).

Goyal, Gay and Lee (2010) examined socioeconomic status as a risk factor for depressive symptoms in late pregnancy and the early postpartum period. Result showed that Low SES was associated with increased depressive symptoms in late pregnancy and at 2 and 3 months, but not at 1 month postpartum. Women with four SES risk factors (low monthly income, less than a college education, unmarried, unemployed) were 11 times more likely than women with no SES risk factors to have clinically elevated depression scores at 3 months postpartum, even after controlling for the level of prenatal depressive symptoms. Matsumura, et 'al (2019) also studied Lower socioeconomic status which is often thought to be associated with an elevated risk of postpartum depression; however, this relationship exhibits noticeable heterogeneity between studies. The result of the study revealed that a lower education level was associated with a higher prevalence of postpartum depression and related symptoms. Although these relationships weakened in the fully adjusted models, odds ratios for cases and related symptoms remained significant at 1 and 6 months postpartum. Among three symptom dimensions, the relationship was strongest and weakest in the depressive and anxiety symptoms, respectively. In a related study carried out by Szurek-Cabanas et' al (2024), it was reported that Postpartum depression (PPD) affects nearly 20% of postpartum women and has severe short- and long-term detrimental effects on their mental health. While there is ample evidence linking depression-related outcomes and individuals' socioeconomic status (SES), the examination of differences in PPD as a function of SES has received relatively little empirical attention, resulting in inconsistent empirical evidence. There are also no well-established systematic reviews on the linkage between SES and PPD. Finally, Fairthorne (2019) carried out a study to assess whether socio-economic status (SES) was related to the risk of a medical or psychiatric hospitalization associated with depression (HAWD) and the risk of a HAWD by anti-depressant (AD) use during the years around a birth. Result of the study revealed statistics suggesting that SES has significant influence on PPD among mothers.

Furthermore, the researcher has observed that depression among post-natal women has effects such as loss of interest, guilt, chronic fatigue, decreased appetite, insomnia, feeling of hopelessness, irritability or frustration, unexplained physical problems such as back pain or headaches etc. A birth of a child, which is usually a time of joy for the mother and entire family, can sometimes have negative consequences when the mother becomes depressed. The consequences of postpartum depression are enormous. Postpartum mothers experience impaired functioning which can interfere with breastfeeding process. It is also linked with negative outcomes for women and infants, such as maternal suicide, weak maternal interaction with her infant, early termination of breastfeeding, and delay in the child's development.

Hence, in the light of these negative trends, the problem of the study is; what is the extent of prevalence as well as correlate of postpartum depression among postnatal women in Rivers State. Specifically, the study sought to;

1. Determine the prevalence of postpartum depression among postnatal women in Rivers State, Nigeria
2. Ascertain the extent to which socioeconomic status influence postpartum depression among postnatal women Rivers State.

The following research questions were as a guide in the research in the study;

1. To what extent is postpartum depression prevalent among postnatal women in Rivers State?
2. To what extent does socioeconomic status influence postpartum depression among postnatal women in Rivers State?

Correspondingly, the following hypotheses were also formulated to guide the study;

1. Postpartum depression is not prevalent among postnatal women in Rivers State.
2. There is no significant influence of socioeconomic status on postpartum depression among postnatal women in Rivers State.

METHODS

This study adopted the ex-post facto as well as the correlational research design in the study. The population of the study consisted of 3,241 postnatal mothers from the selected hospitals in Rivers State which includes University of Port Harcourt teaching Hospital (UPTH), Rivers State University Teaching Hospital, Military Hospital and Obio Cottage Hospital. The sample size for the study was 200 postnatal women drawn using non-proportionate and purposive sampling technique. Two instruments were used in the study which are “Prevalence and Correlate of Postpartum Depression Questionnaire” (PCOPDQ) and the “Edinburgh Postnatal Depression Scale” (EPDS). The Prevalence and Correlate of Postpartum Depression Questionnaire” (PCOPDQ) is designed after the 4-point Likert scale of Strongly Agreed (SA), Agreed (A), Disagreed (D) and Strongly Disagreed (SD). It contains two sections (A and B). Section A contains personal information like the socio-economic status of the respondent, the mode of delivery as well as their desired sex of baby. In section B, the instrument contains information on three subsections. Subsection 1 contains items measuring the level of the respondent’s spouse emotional support. Sub-section 2 contains items scaling the level of agreement as per the proper timing of the pregnancy while sub-section 3 contains information on the stress level of the respondents. Each of the sub-section contains 10 items making it a 30-items questionnaire. Also, the highest possible score is 120 and lowest possible score is 30. On the other hand, the Edinburgh Postnatal Depression Scale” (EPDS) is an adopted instrument from the works of Cox, Holden and Segovsky (1987) originally developed to assist primary care health professionals in detecting mothers suffering from postpartum depression (PPD); a distressing disorder more prolonged than the “blues” (which occur in the first week after delivery). The instrument contained 10 items with maximum score of thirty (30) and minimum score of zero (0). Furthermore, in order to identify mothers with postpartum depression, those who score up to 15 and above were considered as experiencing PPD and vice-versa. Note that only those with the average score and above were used for the study. The validity of the instruments was determined by giving it to experts in Measurement for vetting. Cronbach Alpha method was used in determining the reliability of the instrument which yielded a reliability coefficient values of 0.81 and 0.71, respectively for the “PCOPDQ” and “EPDS” respectively. Descriptive statistics involving simple percentage, mean, standard deviation as well as Pearson Product Moment Correlation was used to analyze the data collected in the process.

RESULT

Research Question One: *To what extent is postpartum depression prevalent among postnatal women in Rivers State?*

Hypothesis One: Postpartum depression is not prevalent among postnatal women in Rivers State.

Table 1 Simple Percentage Analysis of Prevalence of Postpartum Depression among Postnatal Women in Rivers State.

PPD	N	Percentage (%)	Remarks
Number of Cases	76	38%	Moderate Prevalence
Non-Cases	124	62%	
Total	200		

From the analysis in the study, it is revealed that 76 respondents representing 38% scored above the cut-off mark of 15 while 124 representing 62% scored less. This percentage means that there is a moderate

prevalence of postpartum depression among postnatal women in Rivers state, out of 200 respondents, only 76 cases were revealed.

Research Question Two: *To what extent does socioeconomic status influence postpartum depression among postnatal women in Rivers State?*

Hypothesis One: There is no significant influence of socioeconomic status on postpartum depression among postnatal women in Rivers State.

Table 2: Independent t-test analysis of difference in the influence of socioeconomic status on postpartum depression among postnatal women in Rivers State.

SES	N	Mean	Std. D	Df	T	Sample \bar{x}	Alpha	Sig	Result
High	50	18.70	3.099	74	-2.61	16.29	0.05	0.027	Significant
Low	26	20.42	3.252						

The analysis in the table shows that mean and standard deviation for postnatal women from high socio-economic status homes were 18.70 and 3.09 respectively. Mean of those from low socio-economic status homes were 20.42 and 3.25 respectively. This mean shows that mothers from low socio-economic homes face more postpartum depression compared to those from high economic homes. Again, comparing the individual group mean values to the sample mean, it could be seen that socio-economic status has high influence on postpartum depression among postnatal women in Rivers State. The calculated t-value has also revealed a negative influence. This means that as mothers' socio-economic status increases, postpartum depression will reduce and as it reduces, postpartum depression will increase. Calculated sig. value was 0.027. Therefore, since sig (0.027<0.05) is less than 0.05 alpha at 74 degrees of freedom, the null hypothesis was rejected meaning that there is a significant influence of socioeconomic status on postpartum depression among postnatal women in Rivers State.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Research finding one revealed that there is moderate prevalence of postpartum depression among postnatal women. This finding means that some mothers are experiencing PPD and that the incidence of PPD is the same with the previous reports. It also connotes that majority of postnatal mothers are not experiencing significant symptoms of depression. This finding may be in place because interventions and support systems in place may be effective in preventing or reducing PPD. This finding may also be in place because there may be factors protecting against PPD, such as strong social support, good physical health, or positive birth experiences. However, despite these revelations, it could be wise to also consider factors like underreporting probably as a result of mothers not disclosing symptoms due to stigma or fear of judgment. It could also come as a result of sampling bias as it may not be the representative of all postnatal mothers. Furthermore, this moderate prevalence of PPD highlights the importance of continued monitoring and screening to ensure accurate detection. The finding of the study is somehow not surprising to the researcher because as a new mother as well, she knows the joy that comes with childbirth irrespective of the situation of the mothers. The current findings is in support of that which was reported earlier by Rebryatie & Trangenstein (2022), Rong et'al (2023) and Ricci et'al (2023) who all reported findings to support the prevalence of postpartum depression among postnatal mothers.

Research finding two has revealed that socio-economic status has significant influence on postpartum depression among postnatal women in Rivers State. The finding also revealed that there is difference in the influence of high and low socio-economic status. These findings mean that women from lower socio-economic status backgrounds are more likely to experience PPD which may be due to increased stress, financial struggles, and limited access to resources. Again, it could also mean that women from higher SES backgrounds may experience PPD due to different factors, such as societal pressure, expectations, and isolation. On the other hand, the findings means that women from low SES background may lack the basic amenities and may experience increased financial stress, limited access to healthcare and resources, higher likelihood of single parenthood, greater exposure to violence and trauma and this may constitute a

psychological burden which in turn can lead to stress. It should be noted that the relationship between SES and PPD is complex, and different factors may also add to the state of the current findings. The finding of the study is expected by the researcher because she is aware of the influence of economic status of psychology of individuals as those with low status are more likely to experience mental health issues than those from high economic status. The present finding is in line with the finding of Goyal, Gay & Lee (2010) and that of Ricci et'al (2023) who all reported significant influence of socio-economic status on PPD among postnatal mothers.

CONCLUSION

Although the prevalence of postpartum depression among women is moderate, there is a complex interplay of factors contributing to postpartum depression (PPD) among postnatal mothers and this include socio-economic status. These findings underscore the importance of comprehensive postpartum care, including mental health screening, stress management, and emotional support.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations are made for the study;

1. Psycho education therapy should be incorporated as a key intervention for women to effectively manage depression. Also, adequate sensitization should be given especially during prenatal period in order to eradicate any form of PPD.
2. Based on findings two, which revealed that socio-economic status has a high influence on PPD and there is a significant influence of socioeconomic status on postpartum depression among postnatal women in Rivers State, it is recommended that government should subsidize the cost of antenatal services to bridge the gap that may arise as a result of inability to afford medical bills. Again, those from low economic homes should ensure they carry out adequate family planning before they decide on having new babies.

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